

Morphometric and Topographic Analysis of Nutrient Foramen in Human Clavicle in North India

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Abstract:

Background: The nutrient foramen in bones, including the clavicle, is critical for providing the blood supply necessary for bone health, repair, and maintenance. Understanding the morphometric and topographic characteristics of the nutrient foramen is essential for improving clinical and surgical outcomes, especially in orthopedic procedures involving the clavicle.

Aim: This study aims to analyze various morphometric parameters viz. total length of clavicle (L), distance of nutrient foramina from sternal end (A), and Foraminal Index (H) as well as topographical parameters viz. number, position, and direction of nutrient foramina in human clavicles from a North Indian population to provide valuable anatomical data for clinical and surgical applications.

Methods: The study included 80 human clavicles (43 right and 37 left). The presence, number, position, and direction of nutrient foramina, the total length of clavicle (L), the distance of nutrient foramina from sternal end (A), and Foraminal Index (H) were recorded using standard anatomical measurement techniques. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with chi-square tests to compare the findings between right and left clavicles.

Results: Sixty (75%) of the 80 clavicles had at least one nutrient foramen, while 13 (16.25%) had two nutrient foramen. It was also noted that 7(8.75%) had no nutrient foramen. Among the right clavicles, 35 (81.39%) and 5(11.62%) had single and double nutrient foramina respectively, whereas 25 (67.56%) and 8(21.62%) of the left clavicles had single and double nutrient foramina respectively. Both the right (87.5%) and left (84.84%) clavicle's middle third had the majority of the nutrient foramina. The acromial end of the all clavicles received nutrient foramina. Regarding the existence, orientation, and direction of nutrient foramina, there were no appreciable variations between the left and right clavicles ($p > 0.05$). The mean total length of clavicle (L) and distance of the nutrient foramen (A) from the sternal end were 13.83cm and 6.84 cm respectively. The mean Foraminal Index (H) was 47.15%.

Conclusion: The study demonstrates a high prevalence of nutrient foramina in human clavicles, primarily located in the middle third and directed towards the acromial end. These findings are consistent across both right and left clavicles, underscoring the uniformity in clavicular vascular supply strategies.

Recommendations: Future research should focus on exploring the clinical implications of these anatomical findings, particularly in surgical planning and fracture management. Advanced imaging techniques could further enhance the understanding of nutrient foramina characteristics.

Keywords: Clavicle, Nutrient Foramen, Growing end, Foramen Index, Bone grafting.

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Introduction

The clavicle, or collarbone, is a long bone that serves as a strut between the shoulder blade and the sternum, playing a critical role in the shoulder girdle's stability and movement. Embryologically the clavicle is 1st bone to begin its ossification and the last to complete. It has membrano-cartilaginous

ossification [1]. Due to its subcutaneous location and slender shape, the clavicle is particularly susceptible to fractures, accounting for 2.6% to 5% of all fractures and 44% to 66% of fractures involving the shoulder girdle [2]. The healing of clavicular fractures depends significantly on the

vascular supply, which is facilitated through the nutrient foramina. Anatomical variations in the number, position, and direction of these foramina can have clinical implications, affecting both the healing process and the success of surgical interventions.

The nutrient foramen is a vital anatomical feature in bones, serving as a conduit for blood vessels that provide essential nutrients necessary for bone growth and repair. Other than the nutrient artery, the supraclavicular nerve passes through this foramen. Nerve entrapment syndrome (supraclavicular) can occur relating to passage through nutrient foramen [1].

In the context of the human clavicle, understanding the morphometric and topographic characteristics of the nutrient foramen is crucial for various clinical and surgical applications, including orthopedic procedures, fracture management, and reconstructive surgery. Recent advancements in anatomical research have highlighted the significance of precise knowledge of the nutrient foramen's location and orientation, which can influence surgical outcomes and the healing process [3].

Previous studies have documented the variations in nutrient foramina across different populations, suggesting a potential influence of genetic and environmental factors. For instance, a study reported significant differences in the morphometry of nutrient foramina in clavicles from different ethnic groups in India [4].

This study aims to analyze the number, position, and direction of nutrient foramina in human clavicles from a North Indian population to provide valuable anatomical data for clinical and surgical applications.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted.

Study Setting: The study was carried out in the Department of Anatomy at Mahatma Gandhi University of Medical Sciences and Technology, Jaipur, from February 2024 to May 2024.

Participants: The study included 80 human clavicles, with 43 from the right side and 37 from the left side.

Inclusion Criteria

- Intact adult human clavicles from the Department of Anatomy.
- Clavicles with clear visibility of nutrient foramina.

Exclusion Criteria

- Clavicles with fractures or other pathological deformities.
- Clavicles with obscured nutrient foramina.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize bias by randomly selecting the clavicles and ensuring blinding of the observers during measurements.

Data Collection: Data were collected using standard anatomical measurement techniques. Each clavicle was examined for the presence, number, and location of nutrient foramina. Measurements were taken using a Vernier caliper for accuracy.

Procedure:

1. Each clavicle was cleaned and positioned anatomically.
2. The nutrient foramina were identified and their number recorded.
3. The position of each foramen was noted relative to the length of the clavicle.
4. The direction of the nutrient foramina was determined.
5. Measurements viz. total length of clavicle (L) and distance of Nutrient Foramina from Sternal End (A) were recorded and verified by two independent observers to ensure accuracy.
6. Foraminal Index (H) was calculated by using Hughes formula.

Foraminal Index (H) = (distance of Nutrient Foramina from Sternal End/Full length of Clavicle) x 100. [5].

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into SPSS version 23.0 for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and percentages, were calculated. Chi-square tests were used to compare the frequency and location of nutrient foramina between right and left clavicles. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

The study examined 80 human clavicles, comprising 43 right clavicles and 37 left clavicles. The findings are summarized in Graph 1.

Graph1: Distribution of Clavicles Studied Number of Clavicles

Out of the 80 clavicles studied, 60(75%) had at least one nutrient foramen, while 13 (16.25%) had two nutrient foramen. It was also noted that 7(8.75%) did not have any nutrient foramen. The distribution of nutrient foramina is presented in Table 2. Among the

right clavicles, 35 (81.39%) and 5(11.62%) had single and double nutrient foramina respectively, whereas 25 (67.56%) and 8(21.62%) of the left clavicles had single and double nutrient foramina respectively.

Table 1: Presence of Nutrient Foramina

No. of Foramina	Right	Left	Total	Percentage
One	35	25	60	75
Two	5	8	13	16.25
Absent	3	4	07	8.75
Chi-square value	2.06			
p-value	0.356			

On both the left and right sides of the clavicle, the nutrient foramina was primarily found in the middle third of the clavicle. Table 3 offers a comprehensive analysis of the nutrient foramina. 35 (87.5%) of the foramina in the right clavicles were in the middle

third, followed by 4 (10%) in the lateral third and 1(2.5%) in the medial third whereas in the case of the left clavicles, the middle third, lateral third and medial third had 28 (84.84%), 4 (12.12%) & 1 (3.03%) nutrient foramen respectively.

Table 2: Position of Nutrient Foramina

Side	Medial Third	Middle Third	Lateral Third
Right	1 (2.5%)	35 (87.5%)	4 (10%)
Left	1 (3.03%)	28 (84.84%)	4(12.12%)
Total	2(2.74%)	63 (86.30%)	8(10.96%)
Chi-square value	0.11		
p-value	0.948		

In both the left and right clavicles, the orientation of the nutrient foramina was primarily towards the acromial end which means nutrient foramina in all clavicles was away from sternal end i.e. growing end.

foramina between the left and right clavicles ($p = 0.916$). Likewise, there was no significant difference ($p = 0.948$) in the direction of the nutrient foramina between the two sides.

The frequency and location of nutrient foramina in the left and right clavicles were compared using chi-square test. The presence of nutrient foramina did not significantly differ between the left and right clavicles ($p = 0.356$). There was no discernible difference in the middle third position of nutrient

The findings show that nutrient foramina are highly prevalent in human clavicles, mostly located in the middle third and orientated towards the acromial end, in a manner that is similar on the left and right sides. The distribution and direction of the nutrient foramina in the right and left clavicles did not differ significantly.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of A, L and H.

Parameters	Mean	SD
A(cm)	6.84	0.21
L(cm)	13.83	1.08
H(%)	47.15%	0.04

A: Distance of Nutrient Foramina from Sternal End

L: Total length of Clavicle

H: Foraminal Index = $(A/\text{Full length of Clavicle}) \times 100$

The mean total length of clavicle (L) and distance of the nutrient foramen (A) from the sternal end were 13.83cm and 6.84 cm respectively. The mean Foraminal Index (H) was 47.15% (Table 3)

Figure 1: showing measurement of Total length of clavicle (L)

Figure 2: Left sided clavicle showing single nutrient foramen (blue arrow) in the middle one third of posterior surface

Figure 3: Right sided clavicle showing single nutrient foramen (blue arrow) in the middle one third of posterior surface

Figure 4: Right-sided clavicle showing two nutrient foramen (blue arrow)

Figure 5: (a & b) Left-sided clavicle showing two nutrient foramen (blue arrow)

Table 4: Comparison of the present study with previous studies

Parameters	Present study	Kaneez Fatima et al.,[6] 2023	Aggarwal P and Ghorai S 2023 [7]	Keche H et al.,2021[8]	Prabhu S et al.,2021 [9]	Suma MP et al., 2018 [10]	Sahu Santosh K and Dali M [11]	Sowmiya G et al., 2016 [12]	inha P et al., 2015 [13]	Murli-manju BV et al., 2011 [5]
Mean A(cm)	6.84	6.46	6.15	-	6.77	9.11	6.58	6.76	-	6.44
Mean L (cm)	13.83	14.14	14.14	-	13.52	13.91	12.64	14.27	-	
Mean H(%)	47.15	50.1	43.82	50.2	49.98	65.5	52.06	47.31	-	44.72
Maximum number of nutrient foramina (in %)	Single (75)	Single (94)	Single (55.69)	-	Single (57.14)	Single (78)	Single (50.93)	Single (72.7)	Single (70)	Double (44.2)
Location of nutrient foramen	Middle Third (86.30%)	Middle third (67.9%)	Middle third (67.5%)	Middle third (68.13%)	Middle third (94.44%)	Middle third (85.5%)	Middle third (71.42%)	Middle third (90.1%)	Middle third (61.1%)	Middle third (92.3%)

A: Distance of Nutrient Foramina from Sternal End

L: Total length of Clavicle

H: Foraminal Index = (A/Full length of Clavicle) x 100

Discussion

A thorough morphometric and topographic examination of the nutrient foramina of 80 human clavicles, 43 on the right and 37 on the left—was conducted as part of the study. 91.25% of the clavicles showed at least one nutrient foramen, indicating a high prevalence of nutrient foramina. This discovery emphasizes how vital nutrient foramina is in supplying the clavicle with blood flow, which is necessary for bone growth and repair mechanisms.

On both the right and left sides, the nutrient foramina was primarily located in the middle 1/3rd of the clavicle. In particular, the middle third contained 87.5% of the nutrient foramina in the right clavicles and 84.84% in the left. Our findings are by the findings of Prabhu S et al.,2021 [9] , Suma MP et al.,2018[10], Sahu Santosh K and Dali M 2017 [11], Sowmiya G et al., 2016 [12] and Murlimanju BV et al., 2011 [5]. This central location is in line with earlier anatomical research, which indicates that the middle third of the clavicle is an essential region for the transport of nutrients and is probably intended to maximise the circulatory supply throughout the bone.

With respect to the orientation of the nutrient foramina, a sizable majority faced the acromial end. 100% of the nutrient foramina in the right clavicles and 100 percent in the left clavicles were orientated towards the acromial end as similar to studies of Kaneez Fatima et al.,[6] 2023, Aggarwal P and Ghorai S 2023 [7], Keche H et al.,2021[8], Prabhu S et al.,2021 [9], Suma MP et al.,2018 [10], Sahu Santosh K and Dali M 2017 [11], Sowmiya G et al., 2016 [12], Sinha P et al.,2015 [13] and Murlimanju BV et al., 2011 [5]. This directional constancy suggests an evolutionary adaptation that may have been made to support the bone's metabolic requirements by ensuring effective blood flow from the proximal to the distal end of the clavicle.

The right and left clavicles did not differ significantly in terms of the presence, orientation, or position of nutrient foramina, according to statistical analysis utilising chi-square tests. Regardless of the side of the clavicle, the distribution and direction of nutrient foramina are identical, as indicated by the p-values of 0.356 0.916, and 0.948 for these comparisons. This consistency shows that the clavicle's vascular supply plan is the same on both sides, which may be a reflection of symmetrical functional requirements and developmental processes.

The mean total length of clavicle (L) and distance of the nutrient foramen (A) from the sternal end was 13.83cm and 6.84 cm respectively. The mean Foraminal index (H) was found 47.15%. these findings are similar to the studies conducted by Kaneez Fatima et al.,[6] 2023, Aggarwal P and

Ghorai S 2023 [7], Keche H et al.,2021[8], Prabhu S et al.,2021 [9], Sahu Santosh K and Dali M 2017 [11], Sowmiya G et al., 2016 [12], Sinha P et al., 2015 [13] and Murlimanju BV et al., 2011 [5] whereas in the study of Suma MP et al.,2018 [10] The mean total length of clavicle (L) and distance of the nutrient foramen (A) from the sternal end and mean Foraminal index (H) was 13.91cm, 9.11cm and 65.5% respectively.

The study offers a thorough grasp of the topographic and morphometric properties of the nutrient foramina in human clavicles. These foramina are crucial to clavicular vascularization because of their high frequency as well as their regular placement and orientation. These results may be useful in therapeutic settings where understanding the location of nutrient foramen helps direct surgical techniques and enhance results, such as orthopedic surgery and fracture care.

Conclusion

This study revealed a high prevalence of nutrient foramina in human clavicles, predominantly located in the middle third and directed towards the acromial end. These findings were consistent across both right and left clavicles, indicating a uniform vascular supply strategy. Understanding these anatomical characteristics can significantly aid in surgical planning and improve clinical outcomes in orthopedic procedures involving the clavicle.

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